

Prevalence of *Shistosoma Heamatiobuim* among Children Aged Between 4-14 Years in Angwan Ngas Community, Bauchi Local Government Area, Bauchi State

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ABSTRACT

Background: This study investigated the prevalence and intensity of Schistosoma haematobium infection among children aged 4-14 years in Angwan Ngas Community, Bauchi LGA. Methods: Urine samples from 886 school-age children were collected between January and December 2023 and processed using urine filtration to detect and quantify S. haematobium eggs. A subset of 556 samples was also tested for hematuria using a urine dipstick. Results: The overall prevalence of S. haematobium infection was 20.8% (95% CI: 18.1-23.5%), with significant variation across the community. The mean urine egg count (UEC) among infected children was 4.0 eggs/10 ml of urine (95% CI: 2.43-5.52), ranging from 0.4 to 7.7 eggs/10 ml in the community and 0 to 1.1 eggs/10 ml. Multivariable logistic regression analysis revealed no association between age, sex, and S. haematobium infection. Hematuria prevalence was 56.3% (95% CI: 52.2-60.4%) among the subset of participants, varying from 8.3% to 93.2%. Conclusion: The high prevalence of S. haematobium infection in the study area necessitates treatment with praziquantel to reduce morbidity and disrupt transmission among children in the community. Keywords: Schistosoma haematobium, Angwan Ngas, Bauchi.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background: Urinary schistosomiasis, caused by *Schistosoma haematobium*, is a significant public health concern globally. Infection occurs through contact with contaminated water containing cercariae. *S. haematobium* is responsible for most schistosomiasis-related deaths worldwide, with a high prevalence in sub-Saharan Africa, affecting approximately 112 million people (1).

1.2 Knowledge Gap: There is a need for localized studies to determine the prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection among school-age children in specific communities, such as Angwan Ngas Community, Bauchi LGA, Bauchi state.

1.3 Literature Review: Schistosomiasis is a neglected tropical disease with significant morbidity and mortality rates (2). The disease is linked to poverty and poor living conditions, affecting nearly 240 million people worldwide each year (3). In sub-Saharan Africa, *S. haematobium* infection causes hematuria, dysuria, and bladder cancer, leading to an estimated 150,000 deaths annually (4-6). The distribution of Schistosomes is closely tied to their snail intermediate hosts, which thrive in slow-flowing or still waters (7).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area and Population: The study was conducted in six purposely selected schools in Angwan Ngas Community, Bauchi Local Government, Bauchi State. The schools are located 8-10 km from the main town, at an elevation of 720-726 meters above sea level. The area experiences a mean annual rainfall of 654 mm³ and a mean temperature of 25.6°C. The majority of the population engages in pastoralism, while a minority practices small-scale irrigation for farming.

2.2 Ethical Approval: Ethical approval was obtained from the Bauchi State Ministry of Health.

2.3 Research Design: A cross-sectional study was conducted in Angwan Ngas Community, Bauchi Local Government, Bauchi State, Nigeria, from January to December 2023.

2.4 Data Collection: Data were collected using a combination of closed and open-ended questionnaires.

2.5 Sample Size: The sample size was determined using Yamane's formula, resulting in a sample size of 886 participants.

2.6 Data Analysis: Data were entered into Excel 2007 and analyzed using STATA version 11. Prevalence and intensity of *S. haematobium* infection were calculated for each village, age, and sex group.

Multivariable logistic regression analysis, multivariable ordinal logistic regression analysis, and zero-inflated negative binomial regression analysis were used to estimate associations and differences in infection prevalence and intensity.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection among school-aged children in the study area (n = 886).

Variables	No. examined	No. Infected	Prevalence% (95% CI)
Gender: Male	443	343	57.7
Female	443	251	42.3
Education: Nursery	443	271	41.8
Primary	443	378	58.2
Valley: Lower	443	108	21.6
Middle	443	391	78.4

In total, 886 out of 994 eligible individuals provided urine samples. The mean age was 9.8 years (age range: 5-14 years), with 57.7% males and 42.3% females. The sample size and corresponding distribution of age and sex are shown across the six schools in the study area. After adjusting for age, sex, education status, and school, the multivariable logistic regression model revealed: Higher prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection in males than females (P-value: <0.05); Higher odds of *S. haematobium* infection in Primary Education compared to Nursery attenders (P-value: <0.05); Significant difference in *S. haematobium* infection prevalence among schools in the study area (P-value: <0.05); Significant variation in mean UEC of *S. haematobium* among children with different education status and schools (P-value: <0.05); Comparable mean UEC and intensity classes of *S. haematobium* among males and females of different age groups (P-value: >0.05). (Table 1).

Table 2: Intensity of *S. haematobium* in the study area (=886)

Variables	No. examined	Mean	P-value	No. of Light Infection	No. Heavy Infection	P-value
Age in years						
Gender: Male	507	3.4	0.917	93	9	0.765
Female	378	4.7	0.916	73	9	0.766
Education: Nursery	608	2.8	0.001	103	9	0.154
Primary	278	4.4	18	1	2	001
Valley: Lower	508	3.2	0.022	3	5	0.1
Middle	378	5.9	0.325	8	0.8	

The urine dipstick test revealed that 56.3% of the children were positive for hematuria or *S. haematobium* infection. The intensity of the infection was classified based on the color reaction: Weak color reaction (ca. 5-10): 65.6%; Moderate color reaction (ca. 50): 13.0%; Strong color reaction (ca. 250): 16.0%. The strip reagent analysis showed significant variations in *S. haematobium* prevalence among villages (8.3% to 93.2%) and education status (61.9% to 88.5%) ($p < 0.001$). However, no association was found between the prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection and age or sex. Notably, when the analysis was limited to children aged 12-16 years, the prevalence of infection was higher in females (76.1%) than in males (50.6%). The filtration method detected *S. haematobium* in 24.5% of the 556 children examined, with most cases (133) found in this age group. Table 2 presents the results of the multivariable logistic regression model, adjusted for age, sex, education status, and villages, with nursery level (1-3) and primary grade (1-6) as reference categories.

4. DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to determine the prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection among school-age children in Angwan Ngas Community, Bauchi LGA, Bauchi state. The prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection was 37%, 25%, and 23.5% as diagnosed using the filtration method (1,8). A similar study in the same area reported a prevalence of 24.5% (9). However, a decline in prevalence was observed, possibly due to the drying out of swamps that support intermediate snail hosts and distribution of praziquantel (10).

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The study found no sex and age-related differences in the prevalence and intensity of infection, contrary to previous reports (11, 15). Significant differences in prevalence and intensity were observed between children living in Middle and Lower Awash Valley and different villages (15). The intensity of infection was higher in children who did not attend school (7).

According to WHO guidelines, mass drug administration with praziquantel every two years is recommended for school-age children living in areas with a prevalence of 10-50% (8). An integrated approach involving clean water, sanitation, hygiene programs, education, and snail control is vital to eliminate urogenital schistosomiasis (9). The prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection was 24.5% (136/556) using the filtration method but increased to 56.3% (313/556) with the reagent strip test (10). Diagnosis using filtration method may miss cases, especially during light infection (11). The dipstick method can be used for rapid screening but may be affected by menstruation and other genitourinary infections (12).

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, *S. haematobium* infection in the Angwan Ngas Community, Bauchi LGA, Bauchi state, is significant and varies in prevalence among schools. However, the overall prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection among children in the community is notable. According to WHO guidelines, school-age children living in endemic villages in the Angwan Ngas Community require treatment with praziquantel every two years, supplemented by provision of clean water and health education for eventual disease elimination. While chemotherapy reduces human morbidity in schistosomiasis, it is not the only valuable public health intervention. Schistosomiasis control requires an integrated approach incorporating health education, water supply, sanitation, and focal mollusciciding, all crucial components of control measures.

Based on this study's findings, we recommend: Further research in the entire Bauchi metropolis to determine the prevalence of *S. haematobium* infection and the presence of snail intermediate hosts, informing comprehensive prevention and control programs; Screening for schistosomiasis should be included in medical reports for newly admitted pupils.

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